

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF ABU JA'FAR SHAMSIDDIN MUHAMMAD IBN
UMAR IBN ABDULAZIZ'S WORK "LATOIF AL-AZKAR" IN ISLAMIC
ORIGINAL STUDY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8424563>

It was a great opportunity to present the book "Latoif al-Azkar" to lovers of Islamic culture. This book was written as a "Pilgrimage Guide" for pilgrims from Khurasan in 552. It was written during the time when the Khurasanites made a pilgrimage with love, and it was the religious life of the Khurasanites that continued for centuries.

According to the content of the book, it can be said that this work, on the one hand, is a guide to the pilgrimage, and on the other hand, it is a description of the graves of the major cities of the Islamic East, from Bukhara to Baghdad, Mecca and Medina, so at the same time, it can be considered a religious and geographical work. You can even say that this book is a travelogue. This honor was given to me by my esteemed friend Mr. Syed Ali Mojani. He announced that the first copy of Mr. Yazdan Ali Mardon was among the photos taken from the Institute of Manuscripts of the Academy of Sciences of Tajikistan.

This copy is considered an important work on Ibn Moza and the pilgrimage. *I wanted to prepare it based on my past experiences. They showed me kindness in this work. From that moment, I started working on it, and in those days I was also on Umrah (Sha'ban 1434), I devoted all the days of this journey to correcting these texts.*

I made some comments about this in the introduction. Here I have to thank Mr. Mojani who provided the copy and also Mr. Alirizo Abazari who read the text carefully once and mentioned his very helpful words and definitions.

My introduction to this work will consist of two parts, first, a biography of the author and his family, and second, the work and its place in Persian religious texts.

Preface to Musahhah

Burhan family and biography of the author

was known as "Oli-Burhan" and "Bani Mozeh" in ancient texts .¹He was one of the scholars and leaders of Bukhara from the second half of the 5th century.

The personalities of Uluru, often scientific and sometimes political, are known in general and local histories, and their works are preserved in the field of science and politics. According to available sources, their lineage goes back to Umar al-Khattab, and they are originally Arabs who migrated to Khurasan during or after the Conquest.

Here in a few sections we will learn about them. First of all, in the records of the late Qazvini, Labab al-albab, he mentioned the list of people named after him and obtained information about them.

Sincerely, these materials are presented in addition to the explanations clearly given on our behalf and in parentheses in each case during his speech. Below is a brief description of this family in the history of Mullozoda, and finally we present a brief biography of the author based on the books of old translators.

A: Oli Burhan in Bukhara

Muhammad Qazvini, based on the sources available in his hand, in the preface of "Labob al-albab" tazkiras, gave information about the situation of the Burhan family, which includes the author of our treatise, although it is ancient, it can be good information about this family.

He writes; Ali Burhan is also called Bani Mozeh. Their families were famous in Bukhara. His father-grandfather was one of the great representatives of the Hanafi sect in Movarounnahr. At the end of the Karakhitai statehood, they were counted among the kings of Bukhara and paid tribute to the Karakhitai. This family is often mentioned in history.

1. Imam Burkhaniddin Abdulaziz ibn Moze Bukhari Hanafi is one of the famous people.²All of the family of Oli Burhan belong to this tribe. He was given the nicknames "Sadr Moziy" and "Sadr Jahan". "Sadr title was used for Qazis and "Sadr Jahan" was used for Qaziul Quzzot.

2. His son, Imam al-Shahid Husamiddin Umar bin Abdulaziz bin Mozemovarounnahr, was one of the famous jurists. In the battle of Qatvan near Samarkand in 536, it was between Sultan Sanjar (552m) and Gorkhan, due to a

¹ For more information, see Al-Burhan's entry in the Great Encyclopedia of Islam (607/1-608) and Al-Burhan's Encyclopedia of Persian Literature 12-1991. Both entries are available and we do not need them. There is more debate about this.

² He was a popular figure and was eulogized by prominent poets of his time. Abu al-Hijah Muqatil bin Atiya Bakri wrote a poem in praise of him, which is included in Haridatul-Qasr (4/379).
"Tabaqat al-Sunniyya", 2/350

mistake, Sanjar suffered a heavy defeat. Imam Hussamiddin was killed by Gorkhan.

(Sadr, martyr Husamuddin Abu Muhammad Abu Hafs Umar bin Abdulaziz bin Umar bin Moza Bukhari (483)-536 AH), a Hanafi jurist known as Ibn Mozai, was from Khurasan. He learned the science of jurisprudence from his father and achieved such a position that he became a zarbulmasal. He had a high rank under the Sultan. Many people learned fiqh from him. He heard a hadith from Ali ibn Muhammad Khuddam, and Ali ibn Wazir Dimashqi narrated a hadith from him. He died in the Qatvan incident near Samarkand and was buried in Bukhara.

From his works: "Al Jame'" from fiqh: "Al-Fatawa Al-Saghir" and "Al-Fatawa Al-Kabir", "Umdatul Mufti wal-Mustafti" "Al-Waqiotul Hisamiyyah" known as "Al-Janas". Method: "Usul hisamiddin", Commentary "Adabul-Qazi" Khasaf, Commentary "Jami'us saghir" Shaibani. in the Hanafi jurisprudence method .

Sadrush-Shahid (483-536/1090/1141 AD) is known as Umar ibn Abdulaziz ibn Umar ibn Moza, Abu Muhammad, Burhanul Aima, Hisamiddin Sadrush-Shahid. [From the Hanafi nobles of the people of Khorasan. He was killed in Samarkand and buried in Bukhara.

He is a commentator on "Al-Jami'" fiqh and "Al-fatwa al-saghir wa al-fatawa al-kubra" and "Umdat al-mufti wa al-Mustafti" and "Waqi'at al-husamiyya" in the Arabic library in Damascus. Khassaf)" and "Al-Jami' as-saghir fi tazkirat an-nawadir's explanation and under the name "tartiybu jami' as-saghir" in Sadiqiya in Tunisia, etc.

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